

Fig. 2. Relation between K_{DXY} and $pK_{H_2X}^H + pK_{HX}^H$ for mixed ligand complexes of Nd^{III} -methylmalonidicarboxylic acids. Acids: (1) succinic, (2) itaconic, (3) chlorosuccinic, (4) thiodiacetic, (5) thiodipropionic.

formation occurs in accordance with the stability constants of the parent complex of ligand X. Contrary to this speculation, the higher value of $\log K_1/K_2$ at least in dimethylmalonic steric hindrance may influence the mixed ligand stabilities. Because of this reason, in plots of K_{DXY} against ligand basicity relating to the mixed ligand system of dimethylmalonic acid do not give straight line relationship between these two quantities.

It may be further established from Figs. 1 and 2 that more significant differences from the values determined for $\Delta \log K$ and K_{DXY} arise only for the various mixed ligand complexes of thiodipropionic acid (point 5). These differences, however, point to the effect resulting from the size of the chelate ring and from the specific nature of the donor atoms.

From the experimental data it is obvious that $\Delta \log K$ is most appropriate for the characterising the extra stabilisation of mixed ligand complexes^{2a}, which has a value close to -0.6 . The disproportionation or mixing constant is resulted from the differences in the stability constants of the parent complexes. On the basis of the data obtained it is further pointed out that the steric hindrance exhibited in binary bis-complexes is not significantly suppressed in ternary complexes of dimethylmalonic acid.

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Mass and X-Ray Photoelectron Spectral Studies of Bis(Acetylacetonato)-nitrosylchromium(I)

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IN continuation of our work¹ on the synthesis and characterisation of bis(acetylacetonato)nitrosylchromium(I), studies have now been extended to mass and X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy of the compound.

Experimental

All chemicals were reagent grade. The mass spectrum was measured using Atlas-CH4 mass spectrometer at acceleration voltage 1500 V, and ionisation energy 70 eV. The complex is directly introduced into the ion chamber and heated to a

temperature of 210°. The photoelectronic spectrum was recorded using ESCA-3 type spectrometer using Al-K α radiation (1846 eV) at a pressure between 5×10^{-9} and 1×10^{-8} torr. The sample was mounted on gold planchettes. The binding energy was standardised using a C(1s) binding energy of 285 eV.

The complex was prepared by the method reported earlier¹.

Results and Discussion

The nonelectrolytic complex¹ is soluble in most of the common non-polar organic solvents but insoluble in water. It is very stable and remains unaffected by concentrated alkalis or mineral acids in cold, however, decomposes on prolonged boiling. It melts sharply at 206°. The mass spectrum of [Cr(NO)(acac)₂] is presented in Fig. 1. Besides the parent ion peak at m/z 280, fragment ions like NO⁺, Cr⁺, Cr(acac)⁺, CrNO(acac)⁺, Cr(acac)₂⁺ and Cr(acac)₃⁺ are also observed. The most intense peak is due to Cr(acac)₃⁺ observed at m/z 151. The origin of Cr(acac)₃⁺ may be attributed to ion-ion interaction between Cr(acac)₂⁺ and (acac)⁺ ions. The molecular ion peak of low intensity, is comparable to that observed for Cr(acac)₃² and the results reported by some workers^{3,4}. Thus, it is evident that the compound is monomeric in the vapour state and this result confirms to the earlier report¹.

The X-ray spectrum of [Cr(NO)(acac)₂] in the binding energy range 395-415 eV is presented in Fig. 2. The N(1s) value of 401.8 eV is comparable to that reported for the potassiumpentacyanonitrosylchromate(I)⁵. The slight increase in the value may

Fig. 1

Fig. 2

be due to the neutral nature of the complex. The higher value also agrees well with the increase of ν_{NO} in its ir spectrum¹ compared to that of the ν_{NO} in K₃[CrNO(CN)₅]⁶. It appears, therefore, that NO in the present compound is present as NO⁺ which correlates well with the N(1s) value of the compound and agrees with that of the parent compound⁵, where coordination of nitric oxide as NO⁺ is already established.

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